

THE GALINDEZ ISLAND GENTOO PENGUIN (*PYGOSCELIS PAPUA*) POPULATION AND TIME-LAPSE CAMERA DATA VALIDATION

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Gentoo (*Pygoscelis papua*) penguin colony population behavior/dynamics have been studied in several seasons since 2015. The detailed observation of bird arrival, nesting, hatch, and crèche has been provided in two colonies at the GAI CEMP site at Galindez Island near the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (former the BAS station Faraday). We inform of the visual survey results of the penguin colonies population, chronology, and dynamics. During the five seasons biologist-winterers provided continuous observations every day/every five days of gentoo GBV and GPP CEMP sites at Galindez Island gentoo colonies. The results of visual observations of penguin population changes are discussed. The data validation experiment provided for photo captures from time-lapse cameras of the CEMP monitoring project of CCAMLR is discussed. During 2017/18, 2018/19, 2019/20, 2023/24, and 2024/25 seasons, biologist-winterers at Vernadsky station (Galindez Island), the GAI CEMP-site, provided daily observations of 15 gentoo nests chosen in the three monitoring sites GBW, GPP1, and GPP2, simultaneously with automatic time-lapse cameras record. The results of visual observations have been compared with data from camera pictures, which registered the same nests. The comparison of the events of lay, hatch, and crèche dates was undertaken. The preliminary results exhibit reasonable correspondence within 0–3 days between visual observations and time-lapse camera data for both seasons. The difference between camera and visual for each event varies mainly in ± 1 and from time-to-time in -3 days for 15 control nests at the three test sites. However, the usual event captured by camera photos has a time delay of 1 (on average) to 3 days (outbreak) between the dates registered by the camera and visual observations. This delay should be considered when the event dates from camera data analyzed without correspondent visual observations. The results of the visual survey and camera records of the penguin population and penguin count show the breeding success is an average of about 1.6 chicks and varies from season to season. Severe weather conditions, like wet snow, significantly impact breeding success in some seasons. That was registered in the 2018/19 season when many birds lost their nests/eggs and had to start breeding again, which extended the chronology dates. The results of the combined camera records with detailed observations are helpful in studying the impact of ecosystem changes due to long-term climate variations.